

CERAMICS IN EUROPE

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A B S T R A C T
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Structure and optical properties of Mn and Cr doped MgAl₂O₄ transparent ceramics with LiOH as sintering aid

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Abstract:

Magnesium aluminate spinel is transparent in a broad wavelength range, from 0.2 to 5.5 μm . It is also capable of hosting a variety of optically active ions. Transparent polycrystalline spinel can be produced using spark plasma sintering; however, carbon contamination is an inevitable drawback of SPS. Thus, lithium fluoride is often used to promote densification, reduce carbon contamination, and improve the transparency of sintered bodies. Lithium hydroxide is an alternative to LiF, with a similar impact on densification but employing a different mechanism. However, the effects of LiOH on spinel structure, dopants, and optical properties are unclear. In this work, we report on the influences of LiOH on the photoluminescence properties of Mn and Cr doped MgAl₂O₄. Limited amounts of LiOH between 0.0 and 0.6 wt% were added to a commercial MgAl₂O₄ powder. Afterwards, the powders were doped with various amounts of manganese and chromium, up to 1 mol%. The samples were densified using spark plasma sintering at 1300°C for 5 min. The samples were characterised in terms of densification behaviour, the crystal structure of spinel, the distribution of additives, optical transparency, photoluminescence (PL) spectra and decay. The results showed that incorporating lithium into MgAl₂O₄ increases the structural disorder, e.g. spinel inversion, promoting the densification. Also, lithium significantly enhances the PL intensity of samples doped with Mn and Co. The impacts of structural changes and charge compensation induced by the addition of Li⁺ in spinel lattice on PL activity were critically discussed.

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